

Conference Abstract

Multi-Scale, Multi-Method Observation and Modeling of Structure-Flow Relationships in Karst Fault Zones

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Abstract

Karst aquifers, while critical for water resources, are highly vulnerable due to their rapid pollution transfer pathways through complex internal structures, including karst networks, fault zones, and fractures. Identifying parameters influencing the organization and genesis of these systems, emphasizing their impact on groundwater flow dynamics, are key point to understand processes and overcome associated issues.

Through a multidisciplinary approach combining structural geology, electrical geophysics and hydro(geo)logical monitoring, the morphological and structural interactions between fault zones and karst networks could be highlighted. By integrating hydrodynamic data, including hydraulic head and flux measurements, the study provides new insights into the influence of fault structures on karstification and flow patterns. The high-density spatial and temporal acquisition of these structural and dynamic elements enables to:

1. better understand structure/dynamic interactions,
2. obtain input data for statistical conduit generation,
3. obtain validation data for simulation and definition of generated conduits.

The results form a robust foundation for improving karst modeling by better constraining structural and parametric representations. These advancements enable more strategic and effective understanding, simulation and management of these vulnerable water resources.

Keywords

Karst, groundwater modeling, critical-zone

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Conflicts of interest

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